

Plant Based Seafood

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Abstract— *Aqua culture around the globe is growing to meet the increasing demand for human consumption, but the human population expands to nearly 10 billion by 2050 resulting in increase in global demand for sea food that climbs to almost 30 percent by 2030 which means we are emptying the oceans of fish and destabilizing the entire ecosystem leading to extinction of various aqua species. The alternative to which is a healthy, delicious and accessible plant based seafood product. With the innovations in this industry, the consumers are provided with resource efficient seafood that tastes, cooks and looks like the conventional option. With no animals harmed in the process, without any fecal contamination, no antibiotic resistance with less or no emission of harmful gases, the plant based seafood provides the consumer with a reliable product having health benefits along with similar taste, texture and color of the seafood.*

Index Terms— *Plant-based seafood, alternative, sustainable.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Most of the oxygen produced on the Earth comes from the water bodies which is estimated by scientists to be around 50-80%. We are drastically causing an imbalance in the ecosystem by overfishing across the globe. In the 1950's, the oceans were abundant with fish, with 22% of available stock being fished at a sustainable level leaving 78% for development. Over the years, things have changed resulting in overexploitation of parts of the ocean. A recent study conducted in 2014 concluded that only 17% of the world's fish stocks were considered developing and extension of many species has lead to a collapse in the ocean ecosystem. Even after being aware of this situation, instead of controlling it we have observed an increase in the demand of seafood in the market and the population of consumers is on a rise owing to the nutrient profile of seafood.

There is a lot of evidence that global seafood demand is growing and will continue to grow around the world mainly for fish and shellfish. High population growth is also projected in low and middle-income countries. Hence the demand for seafood is on a rise which is largely met through production systems: Wild capturing fishing and Aquaculture. Each comprises about half of the seafood produced globally today. Alternative seafood fits into these three key categories from a production cost and infrastructure standpoint. We can make seafood directly using plant proteins, fermentation technology, or using animal cell culture to create cultivated meat. Many of the concerns associates with wildlife fishing will completely be eliminated in these production processes of seafood.

With the rising concerns regarding the sustainability and depletion of animal protein sources, plant based seafood has emerged as the ultimate sustainable option to satisfy cravings while safeguarding the environment. Due to rising incidences of water pollution, seafood is often contaminated and can even result in mild to severe poisoning in some cases. Plant based sea-food is an alternative to the conventional sea food which we eat and by this we can save our ocean ecosystem. Development of plant based seafood can lead to consumption of less polluted food with better shelf life and a satisfaction of

improving the health of our oceans. The major goal is to produce a plant based sea food which meets three major parameters namely taste, price and convenience. Development of plant based seafood with ingredients that can replicate their taste, mouthfeel, texture and nutrient profile can prove to be the solution that can meet the rising demands and satisfy consumers without compromising the taste or nutrient composition.

II. PROSPECTIVE ALTERNATIVES

Plant-based seafood products are mostly available in frozen form. However, there are only a handful of these products that make up the majority of sales. These are available in just a few forms mainly breaded fingers, fillets and crab cakes. Ingredients like legumes are the most suitable options for mimicking the flaky texture of seafood.

- **Elephant yam flour:** Elephant foot yam which is a tropical tuber crop grown in Asia is used in producing plant based shrimp, which makes it convenient to get and all the ingredients used can be easily available, and enhances the taste of the product. Extrusion processing makes the product low cost per unit and provides a versatile range of products. Yam is a plant tuber that has an earthy, nutty and slightly smoked flavor which is high in starch content. Due to the high starch content, yam flour can serve as a great primary raw material during extrusion as starch gives a structure to the product during extrusion.

- **Fava bean flour:** Its uniqueness of protein absorption on consumption makes it better than soy. It is used in plant based shrimp.

- **Tomatoes:** A tomato species was developed by a Spanish company to create its plant-based tuna which was chosen for its shape and texture. The tomatoes are simply cut and peeled then it undergoes a flavouring process, baking it gives it its final desired texture which is required for mimicking seafoods like tuna this technique is called sous-vied.

- **Carrots:** Carrots are crunchy, crispy and have a pleasant taste due to which it is used in the mimicking salmon.

- **Eggplant:** Unami is a seafood alternative to eel made by Ocean Huggers which uses eggplant, soy sauce and algae. The marinated eggplant base in combination of gluten free

soy sauce and algae oil results in a ready to eat vegan sea food product. The eggplant gives a ton of unique flavour to the product along with a comparable mouthfeel.

- Pea: Peas are protein rich legumes and the protein's texture and taste is suitable for replicating the plant based seafood.
- Soy: Soybeans are added to prepare alternative seafood products to act as a binder and serves as filler. It is widely used as a meat and seafood substitute due to its high protein content a main ingredient in preparing plant shrimp
- Chickpea: It is identified that the protein digestibility of lysine and proline was higher in extruded chickpea and can clearly be seen as a leading plant based alternative in future.
- Seaweed: It is used for its umami taste in the alternative seafood segment..
- Navy bean flour: It produces a flaky, seafood-like texture. Algae oil is used with it to add flavour and nutrition to the final product.
- Gelling beads: These are typically used in extrusion to create seafood analogues that produce flakiness, or dry protein bite of fish.

III. SAFETY AND QUALITY CONSIDERATIONS

The plant-based seafood has low moisture content which plays an important part in keeping the product away from the spoilage and hence accelerating the keeping quality of the product. The plant-based seafood is a mercury-free and safe alternative for the conventional seafood as there is no chance of poisoning due to toxins that can be found in the traditional seafood. Use of technological interventions like extrusion, fermentation, retort packaging provides the safety to the product, retains flavour, smell and texture. These technological advances provide shelf-life stability, adaptability for intended purpose and convenience for the consumer as well.

IV. SHELF LIFE CONSIDERATIONS

The shelf life of fresh seafood is usually 4-5 days owing to its extremely high moisture content and improper storage, transportation and handling facilities. This constraint can be subdued by developing plant based seafood with incorporating ingredients like fava bean flour, navy bean flour, pea protein, elephant yam flour etc. along with sweet potato puree which produces a desirable and product with comparatively lower moisture content. The shelf life of plant-based seafood is considered to be upto 12 months when processed with suitable operations and packed in retort pouches which are held at ambient temperature due to low moisture activity resulting in lower food wastage and a cost efficient end product.

V. ECONOMIC AND COMMERCIAL FEASIBILITY

The raw materials used for the production of plant-based seafood are cheap, easily available in plenty of quantity for all seasons which makes the product affordable to all in a cheaper form as compared to different kinds of seafood. The technological aspects required for the production of plant based seafood like extrusion technology, retort processing,

etc. is a one-time investment and can provide versatility in the product with later reductions in the processing cost. Plant based seafood with the same nutrient and flavour profile can be made easily accessible in the areas where the seafood is rarely available at high cost due to the charges of handling, transportation, etc.

The investment activity has continually increased over the last four years and has been doubling each year as new companies are being launched and investors are increasingly identifying the significant opportunities presented by plant-based seafood.

VI. Efficiencies of alternative seafood sector -

Plant-based seafood can be more demand-driven than conventional seafood as producers are able to:

1. Respond quickly to changes in demand
2. Locate facilities close to demand centers
3. Only produce what consumer wants
4. Reduce waste

VI. INNOVATION OPPORTUNITIES IN PLANT-BASED SEAFOOD

According to a recent survey, plant based seafood is a now becoming a more popular choice because of increasing consumer concern about the host of ocean health issues like mercury, microplastics, heavy metals, radiation as well as usage of slave labour, antibiotic use and overfishing. This demonstrates the considerable opportunity for innovation in plant-based seafood sector –

- Humans eat 200-300 different species of aquatic animals as seafood and companies are making just a handful of those products, there are nearly endless opportunities to develop novel products.
- Plant-based products currently in the market are ground or minced or breaded, there's a massive opportunity for innovation that can achieve the flaky and delicate texture of the fish fillet.
- There is very little plant-based seafood in the refrigerated section of the store. More consumer shop for seafood moving beyond frozen and shelf-stable product often shelved in limiting veggie section will increase the visibility of plant-based food and accelerate the growth of the category.

VII. CONCLUSION

The improvements to the product development of plant based seafood can be yielded to provide satisfying products for consumers with a variety of ingredients which provide the similar convectional taste, texture, mouthfeel and nutritive value to the product. It is also free from animal cruelty and contains no harmful antibiotics which in turn have led to increased investments in this sector as it is the future and a beneficial alternative to conventional seafood. Commercial fishing for sea food has caused overfishing, collapsing of the ocean ecosystem, extinction of species which ultimately results in a perishable end product with short shelf life. Consumption of which has risk of poisoning, food infection along with antibiotic resistance in the body and can also give

rise to advanced strains of viruses which are highly dangerous for the society. The alternative plant based seafood comes with a variety of ingredients which works to replicate a versatile range of seafood options and gives various options for a desirable product. This sector is on a rise and is a promising option as an alternative along with its counterparts like cell based seafood, plant based meat etc.

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